

High-frequency self-sustained oscillations of a hydrogen jet flame

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Abstract

This work investigates a high-frequency thermoacoustic instability in an atmospheric laboratory-scale combustion test rig. The flame is stabilized by a single-jet burner, operated with pure hydrogen and with a thermal power of 60 to 120 kW. A parametric investigation of the operating conditions is performed by varying the equivalence ratio and the bulk flow velocity. The measurements show a clear correlation between the equivalence ratio and the occurrence of high-frequency thermoacoustic instabilities. It is also observed that, with increasing thermal power, the amplitude of pressure fluctuations increases. Stable and unstable operating conditions—having the same bulk velocity but different equivalence ratios—are investigated in detail using optical and acoustic methods. The power spectra show that two closely spaced peaks exist in the 4 kHz range, indicating that multiple modes in close proximity may be simultaneously unstable. This finding is supported by a beating pattern observed in the responses of three azimuthally distributed microphones. Additionally, the response of the microphones indicates the presence of transverse acoustic modes. To describe the mode shapes, high-speed OH* chemiluminescence imaging is used from two viewing angles: a lateral view and an aft-end view of the flame. The phase-averaged images show an axisymmetric OH* distribution, propagating at approximately the bulk velocity of the jet. These rotationally symmetric patterns indicate the presence of either a longitudinal or a radial mode. A spectral proper orthogonal decomposition of the chemiluminescence signals shows that the leading mode is rotationally symmetric but also identifies a further mode carrying less energy that being of transverse shape.

Keywords

High-frequency, Hydrogen, Jet Flame

Introduction

Combustion dynamics related to thermoacoustic coupling are a major challenge in the design and safe operation of combustion systems for propulsion and power generation applications. A comprehensive understanding exists for configurations and acoustic mode shapes in which the flame can be considered compact, i.e. the flame length is negligible compared to the acoustic wavelength [Culick \(2006\)](#). In the context of gas turbine combustors, this comprises planar longitudinal waves in individual flame tubes, and azimuthal waves in annular combustion chambers, both of which are associated with low- and medium-frequency oscillations below 1 kHz. High-frequency oscillations, associated with multi-kHz 'screech' tones and acoustic wavelengths that are of the same order of magnitude as the spatial extent of the flame with a Helmholtz number $He > 0.1$, thus rendering it non-compact [Lieuwen \(2012\)](#), are less well understood and also observed less often. Their destructive potential, however, is significant, as oscillations of flow properties in the multi-kHz range can impose considerable and unsustainable stresses on hot gas path components. These oscillations are typically classified as fully 3-dimensional transverse instability modes, and require a significant driving potential in the form of high thermal power density [Berger \(2020\)](#). Thus, their occurrence is most often described

in the context of rocket engines [Hardi et al. \(2016\)](#) or ramjet/scramjet combustors [Buschhagen et al. \(2022\)](#).

However, high-frequency oscillations have also been observed in gas turbine combustors in various configurations [O'Connor et al. \(2015\)](#), including reheat flames [Schuermans et al. \(2015\)](#). Accordingly, efforts have been made to experimentally [McClure et al. \(2023\)](#); [Ahn et al. \(2022\)](#); [Berger \(2020\)](#) and numerically [Zellhuber et al. \(2014\)](#); [Ghani et al. \(2015\)](#); [Hummel \(2018\)](#) investigate the underlying coupling mechanisms. Recreating the necessary boundary conditions in a laboratory setting is challenging due to the required thermal power density and chamber pressure, and as a result, few groups have been able to report on self-excited high-frequency thermoacoustic oscillations [Mangold et al. \(2022\)](#); [Sharifi et al. \(2021\)](#); [Buschhagen et al. \(2019\)](#); [Kang and Kim \(2024a\)](#); [Park et al. \(2022a\)](#). Significantly

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Figure 1. Thermoacoustic test rig equipped with the single jet burner. Top: aft-end cross section to visualize the position of the three azimuthally distributed microphones. Bottom: axial cross section through the entire test rig. Flow direction is from left to right.

lower are the descriptions of thermoacoustic feedback associated with radial modes [Sharifi et al. \(2021\)](#), as the cut-on frequency of the first order radial mode (1R) is higher than those of the first- (1T) and second order azimuthal (2T) modes. However, the bulk of previous work has been conducted for methane or natural gas flames, most often in a swirl-stabilized configuration, which potentially favors the 1T mode coupling mechanism of flame displacement and deformation [Berger \(2020\)](#). For the transverse mode shape, extensive methods have been developed for determining either the spin direction or whether it is a standing mode [Noiray and Schuermans \(2013\)](#); [Kim et al. \(2021\)](#). As the gas turbine industry pivots to other fuels, in particular hydrogen [Paniez et al. \(2024\)](#); [Beuth et al. \(2024\)](#), and adapts new injection and mixing strategies [Faure-Beaulieu et al. \(2024\)](#), swirl-stabilized combustion is likely to be replaced by micro-mixing, jet flames, and axial fuel staging, which present new challenges in terms of combustion dynamics [Park et al. \(2022b, 2024\)](#); [Kang and Kim \(2024b\)](#); [Sharifi et al. \(2021\)](#) and pollutant emission mitigation [Jaeschke et al. \(2024\)](#). It is thus of paramount interest to extend current understanding of thermoacoustic coupling to these new flow fields and propellant combinations.

In this context, the current work describes the occurrence of a self-excited combustion instability associated with a potential radial mode in a model gas turbine combustor operated on pure hydrogen fuel in a jet flame configuration at atmospheric pressure. Similar mode shapes have been reported in [Sharifi et al. \(2021\)](#) for a comparable experimental setup, indicating that such dynamics are not unique to the present burner geometry. The burner closely represents a single jet tube of a real-world application burner, with a power throughput of up to 120 kW. The behaviour and size of this single jet burner is comparable to that of one single jet in the configuration studied by [Krebs et al. \(2022\)](#). For integration of the present findings into full-scale systems, where multiple jets operate in parallel, further analysis of flame–flame interaction is required. Notably, [Beuth et al. \(2024\)](#) showed that such interactions were minor in their multi-jet burner configuration, suggesting that single-jet investigations can still provide relevant insight. In the present study, the mode shape is identified from

pressure time series and chemiluminescence imaging, and the resulting data are used to extract coherent structures by means of phase averaging and the SPOD method.

Experimental setup

For this study, we investigate a piloted single jet hydrogen burner (POShyDON) [zur Nedden et al. \(2025a,b\)](#). A schematic of the burner is shown in Fig. 1. Jet burners are characterized by a relatively simple design: an inlet duct, a fuel injection mixing tube, and a dump plate connecting to the combustion chamber. While the burner and injection tube considered in this study are identical to those considered in previous work [zur Nedden et al. \(2025a,b\)](#), the diameter of the combustion chamber, and therefore of the dump plate, is changed from $D_1 = 105$ mm to $D_2 = 200$ mm diameter. Because the inner diameter of the mixing tube $D = 34$ mm is not altered, the area ratio, which scales with D_2^2/D_1^2 , increases by a factor of approximately 3.63. Although the burner includes a pilot injection stage, it is used exclusively for ignition purposes and is turned off during all measurement conditions. The main fuel injection is located $10D$ upstream of the dump plate, with eight 1 mm holes generating jets in crossflow. Although the burner is developed for fuel-flexible operation ranging from 100% hydrogen to 100% natural gas, in the present study we will investigate only operating conditions with pure hydrogen fuel.

The burner is mounted in the thermoacoustic test rig at TU Berlin’s Chair of Fluid Dynamics. The test rig is illustrated in Fig. 1, and further details can be found in [zur Nedden et al. \(2025a\)](#). A microphone is mounted upstream of the combustor, three microphones are distributed circumferentially in 72° increments in a plane directly behind the combustion chamber. In addition, a fast-response piezoelectric pressure sensor (Kulite WCTV-312) is mounted in the mixing tube.

The microphones (G.R.A.S. 46BP-1) are water-cooled and connected to an in-house built power supply, and their signals are passed through an analogue low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 10 kHz. For imaging the flame, two

cameras are used. A low-speed camera (EHD SCM9701-UV) acquires mean images for each operating condition. A high-speed camera (Photron SA1.1) connected to an image intensifier (Lambert Instruments HiCATT) is used to acquire temporally resolved snapshots for select operating conditions. A 308 nm bandpass filter is mounted to record the emission of UV light associated with the decay of the hydroxyl (OH^*) radical to its ground state. Two planes are captured: a lateral view of the flame and an aft-end view. For the aft-end view, a UV reflecting cold mirror (Thorlabs PFSQ20-03-F01) is placed some distance downstream of the exhaust of the test rig, and the reflected light is recorded. An imaging rate of 40 kfps with a $23 \mu\text{s}$ exposure per frame was chosen for both planes. The pressure sensors are sampled simultaneously at a rate of 50 kHz. The camera shutter and sensor exposure time stamps are sampled at 400 kHz.

The test rig has an orifice at the end of the exhaust for acoustic damping. The cross-section of the orifice is chosen so that the reflection coefficient in the zero-Helmholtz number limit vanishes [Bechert \(1980\)](#), making the system quasi-anechoic at low frequencies, which helps in preventing thermoacoustic instabilities in this frequency range. The exhaust section is water-cooled for continuous operation. Each experiment is performed using partially premixed conditions without preheating and 100% hydrogen fuel. The main parameters investigated in this study are the bulk jet velocity and the equivalence ratio. By varying these two values, the response of the system can be mapped to changes in thermal power and power density.

Investigation of parameter space

A broad parameter study with variation of the bulk flow jet velocity v_{jet} from 30 m/s to 70 m/s and of the equivalence ratio Φ from 0.4 (lean) to 1 (stoichiometric) is performed. This results in a variation of thermal power from 40 kW to 120 kW. In total, 85 distinct operating conditions were measured. For each measurement, a sampling frequency of $f_s = 50 \text{ kHz}$ is chosen over a total measurement time of 20 s. To investigate the occurrence of high-frequency coupling, we analyze the signal of the pressure sensor closest to the flame, located in the mixing tube approximately $1.5D$ upstream of the dump plate. For each test condition, we estimate a power spectrum from the pressure time trace of the piezoelectric sensor using Welch's method and automatically scan for the highest peak. For Welch's method, a flat top window was selected to preserve the shape and width of spectral peaks in the frequency domain. The signal was divided into ten segments with 50% overlap.

In Fig. 2a and 2b, respectively, we show the frequency and amplitude of the highest PSD peak as a function of the bulk jet velocity and the equivalence ratio. In both figures, we overlay isolines indicating the thermal power estimated by the relation $P_{\text{th}} = \dot{m}_{\text{fuel}}\text{LHV}$. At lower jet velocities and higher equivalence ratios than those considered, the flame experiences the first precursors of flashback, if not flashback. Thus, these operating points are not investigated. In Fig. 2a, a correlation between the equivalence ratio and the dominant frequency of the acoustic spectra can be observed: the larger the equivalence ratio, the larger the dominant frequency. Dominant frequencies up to 5 kHz for equivalence

(a) Frequency of dominant peak

(b) Amplitude of dominant peak

Figure 2. Frequency and amplitude of the highest peak detected by the microphone in the mixing tube across the entire parameter range, with a linear interpolation between the scattered data. 120 kW is the upper limit of thermal power at which the test rig can be operated. For further investigation, two points are selected and marked as stable (s) and unstable (u).

ratios close to one are measured. As the equivalence ratio is decreased, we observe a strong transition from the high frequencies at 4 kHz - 5 kHz to low frequencies below 1 kHz. This transition occurs in the range $\Phi = 0.5 - 0.7$, and low frequencies dominate the spectra for equivalence ratios below 0.5. For jet velocities below 35 m/s, high frequencies do not dominate the spectra. This cut-off at low jet velocities may be due to the flame being close to the flashback limit. For equivalence ratios greater than 0.9 and with a velocity below 35 m/s, the first flashback precursors were observed. In Fig. 2b, the magnitudes of the dominant peak in the spectral decomposition are shown. The intensity of the acoustic signals shows a clear dependency on the thermal power: the higher the thermal power, the higher the sound levels. By correlating the amplitude and frequency maps, one can see that high-frequency oscillations tend to occur at higher thermal power and have larger amplitudes, consistent with previous observations in the literature [Park et al. \(2024\)](#).

To gain further insight into this dependency, for each measured condition, mean OH* chemiluminescence images are acquired. The flame length and flame surface area are calculated from these images. The images are converted into a Boolean array by defining an OH* threshold, set to be triple the mean value of the overall image. This threshold was chosen because the intensity of OH* concentrated in a small volume for the shortest flames was saturating the camera resolution. The flame length is assessed by evaluating the cut-off in the centerline and is shown in Fig. 3a as a function of the jet velocity and the equivalence ratio. The flame shape shows slight asymmetries, most probably induced by the fuel injection holder in the mixing tube, which comprises three streamlined struts holding the fuel injector centered in the mixing tube (see exemplary Fig. 7b). However, the influence of this asymmetry is assumed to be minor. Increasing the jet velocity increases the ratio of bulk flow velocity to the flame velocity, resulting in longer flame lengths. Increasing the equivalence ratio, on the other hand, results in shorter flame length due to the higher mixture reactivity. The flame length does not appear to correlate with the occurrence of a high-frequency mode nor with the spectral intensity.

In addition to the flame length, also the flame surface is computed by integrating the area in which the images exceed the threshold. From this, we calculate the volume of the combustion region by assuming rotational symmetry. With the measured thermal power of the flame and the combustion volume at hand, the power density is estimated and reported in Fig. 3b. The asymmetry of the flame propagates into the assessment of flame length, and certainly introduces an error for the flame volume calculation. However, the influence of the error on the general trend should be minor. One can observe that the calculated power densities are significantly higher than those of conventional swirl flames Berger (2020). However, Lammel et al. Lammel et al. (2010) report values up to 110 MW/m³ for a multi-jet burner operated up to 50% vol hydrogen share. The reported power density values correlate well with the measured spectral intensity, leading to the conclusion that an increase in thermal density increases the intensity of the thermoacoustic modes.

Detailed investigation of a stable and a self-sustained operating condition

For further investigation, two operating conditions are selected having the same jet velocity but different equivalence ratios. These operating points are marked in Fig. 2. The thermal-flow conditions corresponding to these operating points are reported in Table 1, together with the frequency of the highest measured peak. The unstable operating condition has a higher power density and a higher thermal power. Both parameters correlate with the occurrence of high-frequency instability, as shown in the previous section.

To understand the nature of the acoustic mode(s) coupled with the high-frequency instabilities, we calculate the cut-on frequency of the first two transverse and the first radial modes at the unstable operating condition. The cut-on frequency is determined by using the following equation that considers the bulk flow within the combustion chamber Rienstra

(a) Flame length L_f scaled by the burner exit diameter D

(b) Thermal power density

Figure 3. The flame length and thermal power density are derived from the average images of OH* chemiluminescence. The flame length is determined by analyzing the centerline intensity, while thermal power density is obtained by dividing the measured thermal power of each experiment by the volume, which in turn is estimated from the flame area in the chemiluminescence images, assuming rotational symmetry to convert area into volume.

(2015):

$$f_{\text{cut}} = \frac{\alpha_{mn}c}{\pi D_2} \sqrt{1 - \text{Ma}^2} \quad (1)$$

with c denoting the speed of sound of the product gas, $\text{Ma} = u/c$ denoting the Mach number, u denoting the bulk flow velocity in the combustion chamber, $D_2 = 0.2$ m denoting the inner diameter of the combustion chamber and α_{mn} the m th root of the derivative of the Bessel function of the first kind J_n . In particular, $\alpha_{11} = 1.84$ (1T mode), $\alpha_{21} = 3.05$ (2T mode), and $\alpha_{02} = 3.83$ (1R mode). The bulk flow velocity u and the Mach number are affected by the mixture's density. To determine this density, as well as the speed of sound, the adiabatic flame temperature and the exhaust gas temperature measured behind the quartz glass are considered. The first is an upper estimate of the real mean temperature in the products, whereas the second is a lower estimate. For the assessment of the product gas density a Cantera simulation

is performed. The calculated cut-on frequency values are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Flame parameters of the two selected operating conditions. Values derived from the flame images and pressure transduce in the mixing tube of the burner.

-	Stable ^s	Unstable ^u
v_{jet} [m/s]	56	56
Φ	0.45	0.7
P_{th} [kW]	81	112
PD_{th} [MW/m ³]	193	171
f [Hz]	340	4726
L_f/D [-]	4.65	3.46

Table 2. Cut-on frequencies for the unstable operating point. The gas density is computed once with adiabatic temperature and once with the measured temperature.

-	Adiabatic	Measured
c [m/s]	902	737
L [Hz]	-	-
1T [Hz]	2645	2159
2T [Hz]	4388	3582
1R [Hz]	5505	4494

For the unstable operating condition, both the first and second transverse modes (1T & 2T) are cut-on at frequencies close to the measured one. For the radial mode, only the estimate based on the quartz temperature is cut-on, whereas the estimate based on the adiabatic flame temperature is cut-off. Because the real temperature distribution in the combustion chamber is non-uniform, and decreases when moving downstream, we consider this mode to be potentially cut-on. In previous work, the diameter of the combustion chamber D_1 was half of the current value [zur Nedden et al. \(2025b\)](#). Because the cut-on frequencies of higher-order modes scale with $1/D$, the cut-on frequencies of these modes in our previous configuration were doubled, effectively having cut-off transverse modes in the 4 kHz range. This explains why these high-frequency instabilities were not observed in previous experiments.

To understand the nature of the high-frequency oscillations, we analyze the microphone data in the frequency domain. The power spectral densities of the signals from the microphones mounted on the test rig are shown in Fig. 4. The figure displays the power spectra of the first axially spaced microphone (Fig. 4a) for both stable and unstable operating conditions. For the unstable operating condition, a prominent high-frequency peak at 4726 Hz is observed. This peak is not present under stable operating conditions. Furthermore, in the frequency range below one kHz, the amplitude of the measured broadband spectrum in the unstable operating condition is higher than the amplitude measured in the stable operating conditions.

The power spectra of the three azimuthally spaced microphones are displayed in Fig. 4b. All three microphones display a similar frequency response. Although the microphone p'_{A3} appears to show a slightly lower gain across the frequency range, the relative amplitudes of the microphones should not be compared because the

microphones have not been relatively calibrated in this high-frequency range. Around the dominant high-frequency peak at 4726 Hz, we observe in the power spectrum a second peak with a similar gain and a close frequency, only 40 Hz below the frequency of the highest peak. This may suggest that not one, but two unstable modes are present at this operating condition. To further understand the mode shapes, the microphone signals are bandpass filtered at 4726 Hz with a 200 Hz band. The filtered signals are plotted in Fig. 5, where we also display three different time traces, each for 1 ms, displaying approximately 5 zero crossings of the signals.

The non-constant modulation of the signals in the azimuthally distributed microphones suggests that a transverse mode participates in the dynamics. We stress that the amplitudes in the short time scale insets do not have identical amplitude scaling. On the contrary, these amplitudes significantly vary across the three time traces. This is also visible in the long time scale inset at the top of Fig. 5, where an intermittent/beating motion is evident. The presence of a beating phenomenon in the time series is consistent with the existence of two modes having close-by frequencies and participating into the thermoacoustic oscillation dynamics. Not both of these modes need to be transverse modes. To further support this, we recall that at high frequencies, the modal density in cylindrical ducts becomes significantly higher due to the increasing number of permissible eigenmodes. For example, for a cylindrical duct of length L and radius R with close-open boundary conditions the acoustic eigenmodes are

$$f_{l,m,n} = \frac{c}{2\pi} \sqrt{\left(\frac{2l+1}{2L}\pi\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\alpha_{mn}}{R}\right)^2} \quad l, m, n \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

where the integers l, m, n denote the longitudinal, azimuthal and radial wavenumbers. Because $R \ll L$, modes with similar frequencies but different longitudinal wavenumbers tend to cluster around modes having an azimuthal/radial component. This higher modal density means that modes with closely spaced eigenfrequencies are more likely to coexist.

Investigation of self-sustained high-frequency instability through OH* chemiluminescence

The low number of microphones and the lack of relative calibration between them in the high-frequency range prevents us to reconstruct the shapes of the two modes contributing in the oscillation from the pressure time series. Furthermore, for a clear identification of the mode shape, a microphone array distributed across the burner front plate would be beneficial, as used for example in [Sharifi et al. \(2021\)](#); [Schwing and Sattelmayer \(2013\)](#). To further determine the mode shape, we investigate high-speed OH* chemiluminescence line-of-sight images. By using the camera's gating signal and the pressure sensor closest to the flame, a phase average is created, and shown in Fig. 6 for both the lateral view through the quartz glass combustion chamber and the aft-end view through the orifice using a UV mirror.

(a) Power spectrum of the first azimuthally distributed microphone for both operating conditions listed in Tab. 1.

(b) Power spectrum for the three azimuthally distributed microphones at the same axial position downstream of the combustion chamber.

Figure 4. Microphone signal PSDs. All microphones record an intense peak at 4.7 kHz in the unstable configuration. In contrast, in the high-frequency range above 3 kHz, no significant gain is observed for the stable operating condition (see inset (a)). Closer investigation in the 4.7 kHz region shows that two peaks with closely spaced frequencies are present in this range (shown in inset (b) only).

Figure 5. Bandpass-filtered time traces of the azimuthally distributed microphones. The top plot shows a 2 s interval, and the lower three plots show each 5 zero crossings for selected time periods.

From the lateral perspective, approximately 85,000 frames are recorded with a resolution of 192 px by 176 px, while for

the aft-end perspective, around 225,000 frames are recorded with a resolution of 112 px by 176 px. In the phase averaging

Figure 6. Phase averaged chemiluminescence images of the unstable operating condition. Left column: lateral view of the burner. Right column: aft-end view of the flame.

process, the mean value is subtracted, and 16 phases are grouped. Four phases, with a relative increment of $\pi/2$, are shown in Fig. 6. For all phases, a distinct structure is noticeable, symmetric across the y -axis, with a peak intensity fluctuation of 9% from the mean. Coherent spatial structures are identified by the averaging process, separated by $\lambda = 1.152$ cm. The characteristic propagation velocity is determined as $v_p = \lambda f \approx 54$ m/s, nearly matching the bulk jet velocity v_{jet} of 56 m/s, demonstrating that the flame responds to flow disturbances generated by the impinging acoustic waves. This velocity represents the convective transport of disturbances by the flow, not an acoustic velocity, and it is crucial to recognize that the chemiluminescence fields therefore reflect this convection along the flame rather than the acoustic field itself.

This characteristic wavelength fits approximately 7 to 8 times along the axial extension of the flame, emphasizing the non-compact nature of the heat release rate dynamics

at this high frequency. The aft-end view shows a rotational symmetry with the intensity fluctuation fluctuating from the center outward. For $\phi = 0$ and $\phi = \pi$, a zero crossing of the phase can be observed. This may indicate that the observed mode is not longitudinal, but rather the first radial mode. This idea is further supported by the fact that, for radial modes, the line-of-sight integration from the lateral view should cancel out acoustic contributions. Indeed, the intensity of the averaged images is always low along the centerline $y = 0$. This remains, however, an inconclusive observation because the reported OH^* field is not a direct measure of the acoustic field. Nonetheless, the phase averaging results clearly rule out that a transverse mode is carrying the highest energy content associated with the dominant peak at 4726 Hz.

The phase average shows only the dynamics at 4726 Hz, and the contribution from the neighboring secondary peak at 4685 Hz is filtered out. Since the microphones clearly indicated an overlay of two signals, one of which with

Figure 7. (a): SPOD mode energy. Green: stable conditions. Orange: unstable conditions. (b): Mean OH^* intensity. Top: stable conditions. Bottom: unstable conditions.

a transverse component, a spectral proper orthogonal decomposition (SPOD) is performed [Schmidt and Colonius \(2020\)](#). We choose a bin size of $N_{\text{fft}} = 512$ and an overlap of 50% for the analysis. The size of the bin is chosen to achieve a reasonable compromise between spatial resolution and frequency resolution. The frequency resolution is approximately 80 Hz, which bundles together both peaks at 4.7 kHz observed in the spectrum of the microphone signals. In Fig. 7a, we show the energy content of the first 4 SPOD modes for both stable and unstable operating conditions, together with the mean OH^* intensities.

As observed with the microphones, the high frequency peak above 4 kHz is only visible for the unstable operating conditions. Furthermore, the amplitude of the broad-band energy content at low frequencies is increased for the unstable operating condition. For both operating conditions, there is a leading mode that carries most of the energy compared to the other modes throughout the spectrum. Focusing on the unstable mode only, the real part of the mode shapes associated with the peak at 4.7 kHz of the first four leading modes, labeled from 0 to 3, are plotted for both the lateral and aft-end view in Fig. 8 in descending energy content. Note that the aft-end and lateral views are from two separate, unsynchronized recordings.

Mode 0 has the highest energy share and has a structure analogous to that found when phase-averaging the data. Mode 1 also has a symmetric structure along the y -axis but has a more complex structure close to the burner exit, for $x/D < 1$, but a non-axisymmetric structure along the aft-end view. The rotationally symmetric and non-symmetric difference in the two views of mode 1 can stem from the separate measurements taken for SPOD reconstruction. It is likely that the influence of the symmetric mode is smaller in the aft end view, resulting in a higher influence of transverse disturbances. Modes 2 and 3 show an antisymmetric pattern

from the lateral view, which could be associated with the first transverse mode. This is confirmed also from the aft-end view, which exhibits a clear flapping structure.

The SPOD results indicate that a possible overlay of two modal structures, one associated with a longitudinal or radial acoustic mode with no transverse component, and one with a mode with a transverse component, is found in the modal decomposition. The observed discrepancy between the rotationally symmetric and non-symmetric patterns of mode 1 could stem from the separate measurements used for SPOD reconstruction, as it is probable that the energy contribution of the two modes is not identical between measurements, leading to a stronger relative influence of transverse disturbances in the aft-end view.

Conclusions

This study investigated high-frequency thermoacoustic instabilities in a hydrogen jet flame under atmospheric conditions. A broad range of operating conditions was investigated, by varying the mass flow rate and equivalence ratio. The experiments demonstrate that high-frequency instabilities occur predominantly at higher equivalence ratios and jet velocities, conditions associated with increased thermal power and power density. The power spectral densities revealed two closely spaced peaks around 4.7 kHz, indicating the simultaneous presence of multiple acoustic modes. Beating patterns in the time series confirmed the interaction of these modes, with further analysis suggesting contributions from both longitudinal or radial modes, and transverse modes. Phase-averaged OH^* chemiluminescence imaging confirmed a non-acoustically-compact distribution of the heat release rate, with the dominant coherent structures exhibiting rotational symmetry. An SPOD analysis provided evidence of contributions from multiple modes, revealing a leading symmetric mode alongside transverse

Figure 8. First four modes of the SPOD for the unstable operating condition. The right column displays the lateral view, and the right column displays the aft-end view.

modes, emphasizing the multi-mode nature of the instability. Furthermore, the findings from Sharifi et al. (2021) for a comparable burner setup operated with methane demonstrate that the first radial mode can be experimentally identified. This observation is in good agreement with the present results, supporting the hypothesis of a radial mode contribution in the current hydrogen-fueled configuration.

This work highlights the critical role of thermal power density in driving high-frequency instabilities, which is a critical factor for hydrogen-fueled combustors. Further understanding of the coupling mechanisms between non-compact flames and acoustic fields is crucial for mitigating oscillations and improving the stability of next-generation combustion technologies.

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